

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
FLOWER SHOP BILLING MANAGEMENT
SYSTEM PROJECT
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CHAPTER 1

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this project is to automate the booking system of a flower shop through the computer with satisfactory user interactions. The developed software will be easier and more flexible to handle. Computerization of the booking system will be able to give fast services to the customers. We chose this system because it is more efficient, it is cost effective and manual errors will be lessened. This includes a variety of collections of flowers and flower made products such as flower arrangements, flower bouquets etc. This project deals with the booking of various flower products to the various customers, updating and editing of flower products rates and searching for employees, customers and calculation of bills. We first check the availability of the particular flower. Then if available sale it to the particular customer. The objective of the project is to make good software with an overall performance. The software should be easy to work. The software should be able to extract information from databases and make the reports very easily. The software and its operations should be safe and unauthorized access should not be allowed. This is a Flower shop Management and Information System that has the capabilities of that a sales and inventory of flower products.

1.2 EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system maintained the data manually. The data maintenance adopted by the system is not systematic. The personal details about the customers, the transactions made with the customer in various places, Bill of material details, Receipt details, Stock, Packing, each of these are maintained manually in a separate register. Maintaining data becomes difficult, when the details are maintained in the form of hard copy.

1.2.1 DISADVANTAGES

- Highly Expensive
- Storing data and retrieval becomes very difficult.
- It is not computerized and hence not systematic.
- Lack of database security.
- Same data are stored in more than one location.
- Access speed is less for searching and modifying data.
- Products, offers, change in prices.

1.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM

This software is capable of recording details of sales and purchase order. Similarly keeps track of expenses and income of the company. This billing accounting software can be used to generate various reports including Item, Ledger, Sales order, Purchase order and Expenses ledger and more. This software is totally self-contained and works relatively as efficient as other packages related to the subject. It provides simple database rather than complex ones for high requirements and it provides good and easy graphical user interface to both new as well as experienced user of the computer.

ADVANTAGES

- Expense becomes less.
- Large volumes of data can be stored with ease.
- Security is assured.
- Maintenance of file is flexible.
- Stored data and procedures can be easily edited.
- Easy report generation.
- Less manpower required.

1.3.1 HARDWARE SPECIFICATION

- Processor : Dual core processor 2.6.0 GHZ
- RAM : 1GB
- Hard disk : 160 GB
- Compact Disk : 650 Mb
- Keyboard : Standard keyboard
- Monitor : 15 inch color monitor

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- Front End : JSP
- Back End : SQL Server 2008
- Platform : Windows 7
- IDE : Net beans

FRONT END (JSP):

Java Server Page (JSP) is a technology for controlling the content or appearance of Web pages through the use of servlets, small programs that are specified in the Web page and run on the Web server to modify the Web page before it is sent to the user who requested it. Sun Microsystems, the developer of Java, also refers to the JSP technology as the Servlet application program interface (API). JSP is comparable to Microsoft's Active Server Page (ASP) technology. Whereas a Java Server Page calls a Java program that is executed by the Web server, an Active

Server Page contains a script that is interpreted by a script interpreter (such as VBScript or JScript) before the page is sent to the user. Architecturally, JSP may be viewed as a high-level abstraction of Java servlets. JSPs are translated into servlets at runtime, therefore JSP is a Servlets; each JSP servlet is cached and re-used until the original JSP is modified. JSP can be used independently or as the view component of a server-side model–view–controller design, normally with JavaBeans as the model and Java servlets (or a framework such as Apache Struts) as the controller. This is a type of Model 2 architecture.

JSP allows Java code and certain pre-defined actions to be interleaved with static web markup content, such as HTML, with the resulting page being compiled and executed on the server to deliver a document. The compiled pages, as well as any dependent Java libraries, contain Java byte code rather than machine code. Like any other Java program, they must be executed within a Java virtual machine (JVM) that interacts with the server's host operating system to provide an abstract, platform-neutral environment. JSPs are usually used to deliver HTML and XML documents, but through the use of OutputStream, they can deliver other types of data as well. The Web container creates JSP implicit objects like request, response, session, application, config, page, pageContext, out and exception. JSP Engine creates these objects during translation phase.

SYNTAX

JSP pages use several delimiters for scripting functions. The most basic is `<% ... %>`, which encloses a JSP scriptlet. A scriptlet is a fragment of Java code that is run when the user requests the page. Other common delimiters include `<%= ... %>` for expressions, where the scriptlet and delimiters are replaced with the result of evaluating the expression, and directives, denoted with `<%@ ... %>`. Java code is not required to be complete or self-contained within a single scriptlet block. It can straddle markup content, provided that the page as a whole is syntactically correct. For example, any Java if/for/while blocks opened in one scriptlet must be correctly closed in a later scriptlet for the page to successfully compile. Content which falls inside a split block of Java code (spanning multiple scriptlets) is subject to that code. Content inside an if block will only appear in the output when the if condition evaluates to true. Likewise, content inside a loop construct may appear multiple times in the output, depending upon how many times the loop body runs.

COMPILER

A Java Server Pages compiler is a program that parses JSPs, and transforms them into executable Java Servlets. A program of this type is usually embedded into the application server and run automatically the first time a JSP is accessed, but pages may also be precompiled for better performance, or compiled as a part of the build process to test for errors. Some JSP containers support configuring how often the container checks JSP files timestamps to see whether the page has changed. Typically, this timestamp would be set to a short interval (perhaps seconds) during software development, and a longer interval (perhaps minutes, or even never) for a deployed Web application.

5.2 ABOUT MY-SQL

Introduction

MySQL is the world's most used open source relational database management system (RDBMS) as of 2008 that run as a server providing multi-user access to a number of databases. The MySQL development project has made its source code available under the terms of the GNU General Public License, as well as under a variety of proprietary agreements. MySQL was owned and sponsored by a single for-profit firm, the Swedish company MySQL AB, now owned by Oracle Corporation.

MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack—LAMP is an acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/PHP/Python." Free-software-open source projects that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

For commercial use, several paid editions are available, and offer additional functionality. Applications which use MySQL databases include: TYPO3, Joomla, Word Press, phpBB, MyBB, Drupal and other software built on the LAMP software stack. MySQL is also used in many high-profile, large-scale World Wide Web products, including Wikipedia, Google (though not for searches), ImagebookTwitter, Flickr, Nokia.com, and YouTube.

Inter Images

MySQL is primarily an RDBMS and ships with no GUI tools to administer MySQL databases or manage data contained within the databases. Users may use the included command line tools, or use MySQL "front-ends", desktop software and web applications that create and manage MySQL databases, build database structures, back up data, inspect status, and work with

data records. The official set of MySQL front-end tools, MySQL Workbench is actively developed by Oracle, and is freely available for use.

Graphical

The official MySQL Workbench is a free integrated environment developed by MySQL AB, which enables users to graphically administer MySQL databases and visually design database structures. MySQL Workbench replaces the previous package of software, MySQL GUI Tools. Similar to other third-party packages, but still considered the authoritative MySQL frontend, MySQL Workbench lets users manage database design & modeling, SQL development (replacing MySQL Query Browser) and Database administration (replacing MySQL Administrator). MySQL Workbench is available in two editions, the regular free and open source Community Edition which may be downloaded from the MySQL website, and the proprietary Standard Edition which extends and improves the feature set of the Community Edition.

Command Line

MySQL ships with some command line tools. Third-parties have also developed tools to manage a MySQL server, some listed below. Maatkit - a cross-platform toolkit for MySQL, PostgreSQL and Memcached, developed in Perl Maatkit can be used to prove replication is working correctly, fix corrupted data, automate repetitive tasks, and speed up servers. Maatkit is included with several GNU/Linux distributions such as CentOS and Debian and packages are available for Programming. MySQL works on many different system platforms, including AIX, BSDi, FreeBSD, HP-UX, eComStation, i5/OS, IRIX, Linux, Mac OS X, Microsoft Windows, NetBSD, Novell NetWare, OpenBSD, OpenSolaris, OS/2 Warp, QNX, Solaris, Symbian, SunOS, SCO Open Server, SCO UnixWare, Sanos and Tru64. A port of MySQL to OpenVMS also exists.

MySQL is written in C and C++. Its SQL parser is written in yacc, and a home-brewed lexical analyzer. Many programming languages with language-specific APIs include libraries for accessing MySQL databases. These include MySQL Connector/Net for integration with Microsoft's Visual Studio (languages such as C# and VB are most commonly used) and the JDBC driver for Java. In addition, an ODBC inter image called MyODBC allows additional programming languages that support the ODBC inter image to communicate with a MySQL database, such as ASP or ColdFusion. The HTSQL - URL-based query method also ships with a

MySQL adapter, allowing direct interaction between a MySQL database and any web client via structured URLs.

Features

As of April 2009, MySQL offered MySQL 5.1 in two different variants: the open source MySQL Community Server and the commercial Enterprise Server. MySQL 5.5 is offered under the same licenses. They have a common code base and include the following features:

- A broad subset of ANSI SQL 99, as well as extensions
- Cross-platform support
- Stored procedures
- Triggers
- Cursors
- Updatable Views
- Information schema

CHAPTER 2

LOGICAL DEVELOPMENT

2.1. DFDs

A two-dimensional diagram explains how data is processed and transferred in a system. The graphical depiction identifies each source of data and how it interacts with other data sources to reach a common output. Individuals seeking to draft a data flow diagram must identify external inputs and outputs, determine how the inputs and outputs relate to each other, and explain with graphics how these connections relate and what they result in. This type of diagram helps business development and design teams visualize how data is processed and identify or improve certain aspects.

Data flow Symbols:

Symbol	Description
	An entity . A source of data or a destination for data.
	A process or task that is performed by the system.
	A data store , a place where data is held between processes.
	A data flow .

LEVEL 0

DFD Level 0 is also called a Context Diagram. It's a basic overview of the whole system or process being analyzed or modeled. It's designed to be an at-a-glance view, showing the system as a single high-level process, with its relationship to external entities. It should be easily understood by a wide audience, including stakeholders, business analysts and data analysts.

Fig 2.1.1 level 0- DFD diagram

LEVEL 1

DFD Level 1 provides a more detailed breakout of pieces of the Context Level Diagram. You will highlight the main functions carried out by the system, as you break down the high-level process of the Context Diagram into its sub – processes.

Fig 2.1.2 level 1- DFD diagram

2.2 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

Fig 2.2 architecture diagram

Various organizations define systems architecture in different ways, including:

- An allocated arrangement of physical elements which provides the design solution for a consumer product or life-cycle process intended to satisfy the requirements of the functional architecture and the requirements baseline.
- Architecture comprises the most important, pervasive, top-level, strategic inventions, decisions, and their associated rationales about the overall structure (i.e., essential elements and their relationships) and associated characteristics and behavior.

- If documented, it may include information such as a detailed inventory of current hardware, software and networking capabilities; a description of long-range plans and priorities for future purchases, and a plan for upgrading and/or replacing dated equipment and software.
- An architecture diagram is a graphical representation of a set of concepts that are part of architecture, including their principles, elements and components. Architecture diagram can help system designers and developers visualize the high-level, overall structure of their system or application, in order to ensure the system meets their users' needs. Using architecture diagram, you can also describe patterns that are used throughout the design. It's somewhat like a blueprint that you use as a guide, so that you and your colleagues can discuss, improve and follow.

ASSUMPTIONS

Before developing the application, we have made following assumptions,

1. One user can have only one account.
2. One category can have many items.
3. Each user can define his own category list.
4. When a user opens an Account the first time, the balance will be zero.
5. In current implementation of this project one transaction contains only one item but the structure that we provide is enabling us to do further extension if we want to apply one transaction contains many items. For the sake of simplicity and the time constraint we decided to implement the current condition.
6. User can generate the expense report based on the transaction date or category type.

CHAPTER 3

DATABASE DESIGN

3.1 DATA DICTIONARY

3.2 TABLE DESIGN

3.3 RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM

Entity Relationship Diagram, also known as ERD, ER Diagram or ER model, is a type of structural diagram for use in database design. An ERD contains different symbols and connectors that visualize two important information: **The major entities within the system scope**, and the **inter-relationships among these entities**. And that's why it's called "Entity" "Relationship" diagram (ERD)! When we talk about entities in ERD, very often we are referring to business objects such as people/role (e.g. Student), tangible business objects (e.g. Product), intangible business objects (e.g. Log), etc. "Relationship" is about how these entities relate to each other within the system.

Fig 3.3.1ER diagram

CHAPTER 4

PROGRAM DESIGN

4.1 MODULES

ADMIN

USER

STOCK

SMS ALERT

MODULE DESCRIPTION

4.1.1 ADMIN

Admin are the type of user and after the registration will be able to manage the whole portal in terms of maintaining all the modules (dynamic and static) and can add or delete the flower details. It helps us to register user.

4.1.2 STOCK

The stock module is helps to manage overall flowers stock details. Here we can insert the new stock, delete the existing stock, modify the stock, and view stock the stock.

4.1.3 SMS ALERT

The sms alert module is helps to manage overall company details. Is used to manage sales items. Sales date, sales item, customer name and so an. This module is also used to collect information about sales that in the flowers purchased by the customer. This input saved in the database. Then the transaction information alert send by the flower shop management.

CHAPTER 5

TESTING

5.1 TESTING

Testing is a series of different tests that whose primary purpose is to fully exercise the computer based system. Although each test has a different purpose, all work should verify that all system element have been properly integrated and performed allocated function. Testing is the process of checking whether the developed system works according to the actual requirement and objectives of the system. The philosophy behind testing is to find the errors. A good test is one that has a high probability of finding an undiscovered error. A successful test is one that uncovers the undiscovered error. Test cases are devised with this purpose in mind. A test case is a set of data that the system will process as an input.

5.1.1 TYPES OF TESTING:

➤ System testing

After a system has been verified, it needs to be thoroughly tested to ensure that every component of the system is performing in accordance with the specific requirements and that it is operating as it should including when the wrong functions are requested or the wrong data is introduced. Testing measures consist of developing a set of test criteria either for the entire system or for specific hardware, software and communications components. For an important and sensitive system such as an electronic voting system, a structured system testing program may be established to ensure that all aspects of the system are thoroughly tested.

Testing measures that could be followed include:

- Applying functional tests to determine whether the test criteria have been met
- Applying qualitative assessments to determine whether the test criteria have been met.
- Conducting tests in “laboratory” conditions and conducting tests in a variety of “real life” conditions.

- Conducting tests over an extended period of time to ensure systems can perform consistently.
- Conducting “load tests”, simulating as close as possible likely conditions while using or exceeding the amounts of data that can be expected to be handled in an actual situation.

Test measures for hardware may include:

- Applying “non-operating” tests to ensure that equipment can stand up to expected levels of physical handling.
- Testing “hard wired” code in hardware (firmware) to ensure its logical correctness and that appropriate standards are followed.

Tests for software components also include:

- Testing all programs to ensure its logical correctness and that appropriate design, development and implementation standards have been followed.
- Conducting “load tests”, simulating as close as possible a variety of “real life” conditions using or exceeding the amounts of data that could be expected in an actual situation.
- Verifying that integrity of data is maintained throughout its required manipulation.

➤ **Unit testing**

The first test in the development process is the unit test. The source code is normally divided into modules, which in turn are divided into smaller units called units. These units have specific behavior. The test done on these units of code is called unit test. Unit test depends upon the language on which the project is developed.

Unit tests ensure that each unique path of the project performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results. Functional and reliability testing in an Engineering environment. Producing tests for the behavior of components (nodes and vertices) of a product to ensure their correct behavior prior to system integration.

➤ **System testing**

Several modules constitute a project. If the project is long-term project, several developers write the modules. Once all the modules are integrated, several errors may arise. The testing done at this stage is called system test. System testing ensures that the entire integrated software system meets requirements. It tests a configuration to ensure known and predictable results. System testing is based on process descriptions and flows, emphasizing pre-driven process links and integration points. Testing a specific hardware/software installation. This is typically performed on a COTS (commercial off the shelf) system or any other system comprised of disparate parts where custom configurations and/or unique installations are the norm.

➤ **Integration testing**

Testing is which modules are combined and tested as a group. Modules are typically code modules, individual applications, source and destination applications on a network, etc. Integration Testing follows unit testing and precedes system testing. Testing after the product is code complete. Betas are often widely distributed or even distributed to the public at large in hopes that they will buy the final product when it is release.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

This application” FLOWER SHOP BILLING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM” avoids the manual work and the problems concern with it. It is an easy way to obtain the information regarding the various flowers information that is present in the markets. This system is an improved application better than the existing one’s regarding the information about the various activities. Still, we found out that the project can be done in a better way. Primarily, when we request information about particular details it shows all the relevant information. This project is a computerized solution for storing the details of all related information in an organization and also task assigned to an employee by an organization. Here, we can conclude that the application been developed is to reduce manpower and various complexities.

CHAPTER 7

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